

Mapping Estonia's Coastal Ridges: A Deep Learning Approach

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Abstract. The coastal ridges of Estonia are important geomorphological landforms for palaeogeographical research and recognizing past climatic events in the Baltic region. The identification and segmentation of ridge-swale complexes through LiDAR-derived elevation data is a vital yet challenging problem. We conducted this study to construct an automated process of segmenting coastal ridge-swale complexes using a supervised U-Net machine learning algorithm derived from the GeoAI Python package. The resulting workflow identifies coastal ridges with an Intersection over Union (IoU) score of 0.51, using DEM and slope as inputs.

Submission Type. Model, analysis, case study

BoK Concepts. [IP3-5] Image segmentation

Keywords. deep learning, U-Net, foredunes, coastal ridges

1 Introduction

Coastal ridge-swale systems are geomorphological landforms composed of linear wave and wind-built ridges of sand and gravel separated by depressions. Due to the unique geographical location of the Estonian coastline – post-glacial land uplift zone and the nearly tideless Baltic Sea - these ridge-swale systems are preserved (Vilumaa et al., 2017, Suursaar et al., 2022). The identification, mapping and analysis of Estonia's coastal ridge-swale systems is valuable because of the information they hold. These landforms are significant for research involving the reconstruction of past climatic and sea level changes, storm events, and prehistoric human settlement patterns (Rosentau et al., 2013, Vilumaa et al., 2017, Muru et al., 2018, Tõnisson et al., 2018, Suursaar et al., 2022).

The existing spatial identification and segmentation methods in analysing Estonian ridge-swale systems have been mostly limited to manual human interpretation. Deep

learning (DL) is a subset of machine learning that uses multi-layered neural networks to simulate complex decision-making while learning from a large quantity of data (Ronneberger et al., 2015). DL models can provide meaningful predictions and have been shown to enhance similar classification tasks through automated detection, and segmentation using U-Net (Hochmair et al., 2025). Therefore, the aim of this research is to investigate the potential use of a supervised U-Net for the automatic segmentation of ridge-swale systems across Estonia.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Data and Software Availability

We used LiDAR-derived digital elevation model (DEM) from the Estonian Land and Spatial Development Board (2025) as a primary data source. We chose a resolution of 1 metre because of its sufficiency for dealing with smaller-scale features. A workflow notebook can be found (Russell et al., 2026).

2.2 Methodology

U-Net in GeoAI adapts convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to perform pixel-wise classification (Wu, 2026). The dataset required for this classification task was comprised of training images and masks. The parameters used for training were a U-Net architecture, ResNet34 encoder, and ImageNet encoder weights set at a learning rate of 0.0003. We created the labelled dataset by visually interpreting the 1 m digital (DEM) of prominent ridge-swale complex locations and digitising the ridges crests as polylines. We buffered these polylines by a width of 5 metres and rasterised to create a grid-based representation for the machine learning input. Each label mask consisted of two classes (ridge and background).

We used LiDAR-derived elevation raster tiles with three bands as training images. The bands in each tile (Figure 1) were as follows: Band 1 terrain elevation (DEM), Band 2 Slope derived from the QGIS slope tool, and Band 3 Topographic position index (TPI), which GDAL defines as the difference between a central pixel and the mean of its surrounding cells. Each band was normalised and corresponded to a channel input. We trained three models to test the best-performing combinations of channel inputs. Model 1 used all three bands, Model 2 used DEM and slope, and Model 3 used only TPI. We used Intersect over Union (IoU) and the harmonic mean of precision and recall (F1) as validation metrics to analyse performance and learning behaviour. We trained each model for 30 epochs, running inference on the best-trained model to make predictions on test images and produce probability maps for visualisation.

Figure 1. An example of the three input bands and corresponding label mask for a single tile.

3 Results

We observed positive trends in learning behaviour with all three models during the training epochs. Firstly, the models were learning effectively, with the average IoU and F1 improving steadily, and the loss decreasing. These metrics suggest the models were improving their ability to correctly segment ridges from elevation data. Based on the validation metrics (Table 1), Model 2 performed the best with an F1 score of 0.63 and IoU of 0.51.

Table 1. Validation metrics summary of the three models.

	DEM Slope TPI	DEM Slope	TPI
F1	0.6214	0.6322	0.5883
IoU	0.5013	0.5109	0.4629

The inference performed also revealed some visual representations of how the model predicted ridges (Figure 2).

Figure 2. An example of the probability inference output and ground truth mask for a single tile using model 2.

4 Conclusions

The findings of this study demonstrate the accuracy of U-Net in identifying coastal ridges from digital elevation data, at a sufficient IoU score. This result shows the potential use of DL and U-Net for segmenting ridge-swale systems. However, while these results are promising the model is not perfect. Additional training, tuning, and sample variation would likely increase the applicability of the model. These further advancements could get the model to a high enough level for implementation beyond a proof-of-concept.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declares that we have not used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

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